

S I N G L E

D3.1 Fabrication of cells and KET components

WP3, T3.1

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Technical references

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Executive summary

This deliverable, D3.1, summarizes the planned manufacture and delivery plan of cells and key enabling technology components (KET) for the time period M1 – M18. The parts will be manufactured in WP3, Task 3.1, and distributed to tasks in WP1 and WP3. The shipments are made in batches within the tasks to accommodate improvements achieved in parallel tracks. The duration of T3.1 is until M30, and the deliverable is re-occurring, with the next version (D3.2) to be submitted in M18.

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1. Introduction

Electrochemical cells and KETs (Key Enabling Technology components) (Figure 1) will be fabricated in WP3 and distributed to other Work Packages/Tasks. A list of components that will be fabricated in WP3 is given in Table 1 and the distribution to other tasks is given in Table 2.

Figure 1: Stack reactor shell (left) and multi-cell stack (right) parts.

Table 1: Overview of parts to be delivered in WP3.

Part	Material	Manufacture site
Membrane cell (Ni-BZCY cell)	Ni – BaZr _{0.7} Ce _{0.2} Y _{0.1} O _{3-δ} support BaZr _{0.8} Ce _{0.1} Y _{0.1} O _{3-δ} electrolyte Ni – BaZr _{0.7} Ce _{0.2} Y _{0.1} O _{3-δ} electrode	CTMS in-house
Face seals	GC654	Powders and firing by CTMS Outsourced shaping
Gasket seal	CG654	Powders and firing by CTMS Outsourced shaping
Interconnect/ bottom manifold	Ni – GC657	GC powders, mixing and firing by CTMS Outsourced machining
Conductive washers	Ni – GC593	GC powders, mixing and firing by CTMS Outsourced shaping

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Table 2: Components distribution from WP3

WP	Task	Type of component to test
1 – Catalytic membrane reactor optimization	1.1 – Improved catalytic activity of Ni-BZCY support	Ni-BZCY cells
	1.2 – Improved stability of Ni-BZCY support under ammonia cracking	Ni-BZCY cells
	1.3. Component compatibility with ammonia	Ni-BZCY cells Glass ceramic seals Interconnects
	1.4 Testing optimized single cells	Reference Ni-BZCY cells Optimized Ni-BZCY cells
3 – Fabrication and validation of catalytic membrane stacks	3.2 – Stack manufacturing	Reference stack Improved stacks
	3.4 – Validation of stack components	Reference stack Improved stacks

The improvement activities in tasks 1.1 and 1.2 can result in changes in thermomechanical properties and are also interdependent. D3.1 will present a manufacture & delivery plan for T3.1. The components manufactured in the task will serve the improvement activities in WP1 in a way that coordinates with the other manufacture activities in WP3 (T3.2 and T3.4).

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2. Activities in related tasks

Since components are distributed to several tasks in two work packages, improvement tracks will run in parallel. Components will therefore be shipped in batches to ensure that improvements are developed based on updated components from parallel tracks. The number of parts to be shipped is based on the planned experimental test matrixes from the improvement tasks.

2.1. Improvement tracks in WP1

T1.1 is led by CSIC and Ni-BZCY cells will be provided to:

- CSIC for infiltration with a selection of metals to increase activity for ammonia dehydrogenation (ADH) reaction.
- CTMS to pursue the galvanic replacement route to introduce Fe and Ru in the structure to increase the catalytic activity.

In M6, two batches of Ni-BZCY cells have already been delivered to CSIC and CTMS for pre-screening activities. At CSIC, cells have been infiltrated with a selection of metals, crushed and sieved into powder and tested in a fixed bed reactor for ADH. The further improvement tracks will be carried out in 3 iterations:

- Initial screening of performance for selection of infiltrated metals and metal loadings (partially done at CSIC)
- Screening of performance for the most promising metals and metal loadings with optimized conditions
- Performance of cells infiltrated with most promising metals and with microstructure optimized for stability in T1.2

The samples for the improvement activities will be delivered in two shipments to accommodate improvements achieved in T1.2.

T1.2 is led by CTMS and Ni-BCZY cells of various microstructure will be provided to CTMS to investigate the effect of microstructure in the long-term performance of the material for the ADH reaction. Furthermore, also Ni-BCZY3 cells, a new variant of BCZY with more Ce in the structure, are provided to test the stability during ADH. In M6, two batches of cells have already been delivered to CTMS for screening activities. The further improvement tracks will be carried out in 2 iterations:

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- Initial screening of cell stability related to microstructure
- Screening of cell stability with optimized microstructure and metal infiltration

T1.3 is led by CSIC, sealed barrels as well as components such as Ni-BCZY cells, cell materials, glass seals and interconnects will be delivered to this task, by CTMS, to investigate the compatibility of these components with ammonia and ADH conditions. Two batches can be shipped at different times.

- Reference components
- Improved components

T1.4 is led by CSIC and optimized cells based on the improvements from T1.1 and T1.2 will be assembled and delivered to this task. The cell assembly will be tested for benchmarking the performance under relevant conditions. Performance testing will be carried out in 3 iterations.

- Benchmarking reference cells under relevant conditions
- Cells with improved stability
- Cells with improved stability and performance

2.2. Manufacture and validation activities in WP3

T3.2 is led by CTMS and components will be delivered to the task for stack assembly. The first stack to be delivered (D3.3) is a reference stack for further equipment commissioning and performance baseline establishment in T3.5. Following, parts will be delivered in two batches to accommodate improvements, where one of the deliveries will be within M18.

T3.4 is led by CTMS and components will be delivered to the task for performance validations. Parameters that will be validated include thermomechanical properties, electrochemical properties and DC conductivity. The first delivery will be of reference components to establish the baseline, whereas the next deliveries will follow a similar schedule as for T3.2.

3. Manufacture plan

3.1. Manufacture methods

Ni-BZCY cells are made on a regular basis at CTMS' facilities. The manufacture procedure comprise the following steps:

- Mixing of ceramic powders with NiO, water and binders into a paste.
- Shaping of the ceramic paste by extrusion with subsequent drying.
- Spray coating the green BZCY-NiO support with BZCY electrolyte.
- Screen printing the BZCY-NiO outer electrode.
- Binder burnout and co-firing the coated green tubes (support electrode, electrolyte, outer electrode).
- Annealing in hydrogen-containing atmosphere to reduce NiO to metallic Ni.

One production cycle requires minimum 3 weeks (including quality control). Including the overall project pipeline it is reasonable to expect 2 months lead time for project-specific cell samples.

For the stack components, powders are mixed in batches and the shaping is mainly outsourced. It is not expected that changes will be made to these parts. The production cycle for a ceramic stack involves multiple overnight sealing cycles, electrical contacting and quality control, and expected time for one production cycle is 2-3 weeks. Welding of the outer reactor housing is done by an external contractor and therefore done batchwise, coordinated with parallel projects. The welding itself is however, usually a two-day job, and the main lead time driver is the sourcing of the lids if they are not in stock, typically 2 months.

3.2. Delivery schedule

The distribution of components to the relevant tasks is listed in Table 3. The components delivered to T1.4 and T3.2 will be used to assemble single tube test samples and ceramic stacks and a surplus of components will be delivered to account for yield losses. For the improved stacks it is assumed that the yield and design are similar as for the reference stack. This is however, subject to change and numbers given in the table are mainly meant to reflect the number of samples/stacks. The time of shipments are listed in Table 4.

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Table 3: Distribution of components to relevant tasks

WP / Task	Type of component	#parts/shipment		
		1st	2nd	3rd
WP1 / T1.1	Ni-BZCY half cells	40	5	-
WP1 / T1.2	Ni-BZCY cells	18	5	-
WP1 / T1.3	Ni-BZCY cells	6	6	-
	Interconnect	1 (6pcs)	1 (6pcs)	-
	Conductive washer	6	6	-
	Glass ceramic face seals	6	6	-
	Glass ceramic gasket seals	1 (6pcs)	1 (6pcs)	-
	Top manifold	1 (6pcs)	1 (6pcs)	-
	Sealed barrel section	1 (6pcs)	1 (6pcs)	-
WP1 / T1.4	Sealed single tube assembly	3	2	2
WP3 / T3.2¹	Ni-BZCY cells	98	196	196
	Interconnect	7	14	14
	Conductive washer	42	84	84
	GC face seals	42	84	84
	GC gasket seals	9	18	18
	Top manifold	1	2	2
	Bottom manifold	2	4	4
	Reactor top lid	1	2	2
	Reactor bottom lid	1	2	2
	Reactor shell	1	2	2
WP3 / T3.4	Ni-BZCY cells	6	6	6
	Interconnect	1	-	-
	Conductive washer	1	-	-
	GC face/gasket seal	1	-	-
	Steel-to-ceramic transition	1	-	-
	Sealed barrel	6	6	6

¹ Design and yield subject to changes, numbers are mainly to reflect 1, 2 and 2 stacks for shipments 1,2 and 3, respectively.

Table 4: Delivery schedule.

WP / Task	Month for shipment		
	1st	2nd	3rd
WP1 / T1.1	M2	M14	
WP1 / T1.2	M2	M14	-
WP1 / T1.3	M6	M12	-
WP1 / T1.4	M8	M13	M18
WP3 / T3.2	M2	M10	M12
WP3 / T3.4	M6	M16	TBD (after M18)

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